

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable 4.1

Report on INITIAL VERSION of Mission ontology and semantic network and guidance for use

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Authors: René Berndt (FhA)

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Executive Summary

Within the P4B project, Fraunhofer Austria (FhA) is leading task 4.1, which includes the development of the Mission ontology as a semantic network for all Mission activities. The initial version targeting developers can be accessed using the link

<https://prep4blue.ddd.fraunhofer.at:7473/browser/>.

For credentials, please contact <mailto:rene.berndt@fraunhofer.at>. After login the semantic network of the Mission Ocean ecosystem (MOE) can be explored using the Neo4j browser. A detailed description of how to use the Neo4j Browser can be found [HERE¹](#).

The MOE semantic network contains currently:

- 35,386 research projects
- 355,710 publications
- 2,121 classification terms
- 49 engagement methods
- 1,268,956 relations between the above elements

This document gives an overview of the development process and the current state of the Mission ontology and semantic network as well as a guidance for developer.

¹ <https://neo4j.com/developer/neo4j-browser/>
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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Table 1. Table of abbreviations and acronyms used in Prep4Blue and the document

Acronym / Abbreviation	Signification
P4B	PREP4BLUE
MO	Mission Ocean and Waters
(the) Mission	Mission Ocean and Waters
ELI	European Legislation Identifier
TGN	Thesaurus of Geographic Names
EuroSciVoc	European Science Vocabulary
EuroVoc	European Union's terminology database
NACE	Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
WP(s)	Work Package(s)
EURIO	EUropean Research Information Ontology
DINGO	Data INtegration for Grants Ontology
CIDOC	Comité international pour la documentation
CRM	Conceptual Reference Model
MOE	Mission Ocean Ecosystem
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
MOEOM	Mission Ocean Ecosystem Ontology Map
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
KO	Knowledge Output
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
DB	Database

1 Introduction

Missions are a new instrument in the Horizon Europe program, which aims to tackle societal challenges with systemic solutions. The implementation of five Missions themes (Restore our ocean and waters by 2030, Adaptation to Climate Change, Cancer, Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and Soil Health and Food) was launched in 2021.

Funded under the EU Horizon Europe program, Prep4Blue is a three-year project that sets the scene for co-creating and co-implementing the research and innovation required to achieve the objectives of the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 (hereafter “MO” or (the) Mission) by using the dedicated enablers “Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System” and “Public mobilization and engagement”.

Within Prep4Blue, WP4 (*“Knowledge Management: Identifying and Transferring Knowledge/Solutions to Support the Mission”*) as such aims to support effective knowledge management, especially in helping to identify high potential knowledge/solutions and effectively transfer them to target end-users for uptake/application in support of the Mission. The mission ontology/semantic network together with the Mission Ecosystem database (DB) will link the various aspects, actions, partners, and stakeholders to support an efficient exchange of expertise and best practices as well as explore synergies and complementarities.

The Mission Ocean ecosystem (hereafter “MOE”) consists of various domains from research over legal aspects to citizen engagement, business model etc. with its specific ontologies and vocabularies. From a knowledge perspective they can be seen as isolated or knowledge “islands”. Using ontology alignment, the MOE will connect these “islands”. Ontology alignment makes sure that two different sets of information, often represented using different categories or terms, can work together and understand each other. It's comparable to translating between two languages to ensure that even though the words might be different, the meaning behind them matches up.

In the digital world, different computer systems or databases might use their own ways to organize and describe information. Ontology alignment helps to find common ground between these different ways of organizing information. In the sense of a map that says, "This term in system A is the same as that term in system B."

For example, if one system talks about "cars" and another talks about "automobiles," ontology alignment helps us realize that these terms essentially mean the same thing, so when these systems need to work together, they understand each other's language. It's about finding connections between different ways of expressing information so that computers can share and use data more easily.

This document is divided into two parts addressing different target audiences:

Part 1:

Chapter 2 to 4 give a short introduction of Ontologies and Semantic Networks and how they will apply to the project. The target audience for these chapters are non-technical partners and users of the MOE ontology and the semantic network.

Part 2:

Chapter 5 to 6 targets developers and gives guidelines for usage and implementing the MOE semantic network. Therefore, the language used in this section is technical and not easily understandable by those outside of developers who are the target audience.

Part 1: Introduction to Ontologies and Semantic Networks

2 Ontology

This chapter provides an introduction to the fundamental concepts of ontologies and semantic networks, outlining the essential terms and ideas. Additionally, it delves into the developmental processes associated with ontologies. The focus of this chapter is on elucidating the key principles and stages involved in understanding and constructing ontologies.

2.1 Definitions

Ontology is a branch of philosophy and computer science that deals with the study of existence, categorization, and the relationships between different entities or concepts within a specific domain of knowledge. In the context of computer science and information systems, ontologies are used to represent and organize knowledge in a structured and formal manner. They define a set of concepts, their attributes, and the relationships between these concepts, providing a framework for understanding and reasoning about a particular domain. Ontologies are commonly used in fields like artificial intelligence, knowledge management, and the Semantic Web to enable machines to understand and interpret information more effectively.

A **semantic network** is a graphical representation of knowledge or information in the form of nodes (representing concepts or entities) and edges (representing relationships or links between these concepts). Semantic networks are used to model and organize structured information in a way that reflects the meaning and associations between different elements. Semantic networks can be used to represent various types of information, such as hierarchical taxonomies, concept maps, and ontologies, to facilitate the understanding and retrieval of knowledge.

To break these two definitions down:

Ontology is a structured way of organizing information to help computers and people understand concepts and their relationships. They consist of the following three components:

- **Classes:** These are categories or groups that things belong to. For example, "Animals" can be a class.
- **Properties:** These are characteristics or attributes that describe classes. For instance, "hasLegs" could be a property of the class "Animals."
- **Individuals:** These are specific instances or examples of classes. If "Dog" is a class, then your pet dog, named "Buddy," is an individual.

Ontology helps to define and connect these elements. For instance, it can say that a "Dog" is a type of "Animal" and that it has the property "hasLegs" with a value of 4.

Ontologies organize information in a way that makes sense to both humans and computers. It promotes consistency in how information is stored and used, making it easier for different systems to understand and share data.

Example: Imagine a library. The classes could be "Books," "Authors," and "Genres." Properties might include "hasAuthor" and "hasGenre." The individual "Harry Potter" is a book, written by the author "J.K. Rowling," belonging to the "Fantasy" genre.

So why do we not have not a single ontology that fits all? Creating a universal ontology for the entire world is a challenging task for several reasons:

1. Diversity of Knowledge Domains:
 - The world is incredibly diverse, and knowledge spans a vast array of domains such as science, culture, technology, and more. A one-size-fits-all ontology might not adequately capture the intricacies of each specialized field.
2. Changing Knowledge:
 - Knowledge is dynamic and constantly evolving. New discoveries, technological advancements, and shifts in cultural understanding happen regularly. Maintaining a single, up-to-date ontology for the entire world would be practically impossible.
3. Interdisciplinary Nature:
 - Many fields overlap, and interdisciplinary work is common. A rigid, universal ontology might struggle to accommodate the nuanced relationships between different domains.
4. Cultural and Linguistic Variations:
 - Different cultures and languages have unique ways of expressing and categorizing concepts. A global ontology might not appropriately represent the diversity of cultural perspectives and linguistic nuances.
5. Context Dependence:
 - The meaning of terms and concepts often depends on the context in which they are used. A global ontology might oversimplify or misrepresent concepts by ignoring context-specific meanings.
6. Privacy and Security Concerns:
 - A universal ontology would need to handle sensitive information. Managing and securing such a system on a global scale raises significant privacy and security concerns.
7. Governance and Control:
 - Determining who gets to define and control a global ontology raises governance issues. Different communities may have conflicting interests and perspectives on how concepts should be represented.

Instead of a single, world ontology, the approach often taken is to develop domain-specific ontologies tailored to particular fields or applications. These smaller ontologies can then be linked or integrated as needed, allowing for more flexibility and adaptability in representing diverse knowledge. The idea is to build interoperability between ontologies rather than imposing a singular, overarching structure.

The following section gives an overview of the workflow for designing a domain-specific ontology.

2.2 Development Workflow

Figure 1 Ontology Development Workflow

Following the workflow (see Figure 1) for developing an ontology the following actions have been carried out respectively are ongoing:

1. Define the Domain and Purpose/Consider reuse:

In this context, the ontology's specific domain or subject of focus is determined. For the project PREP4BLUE the domain is the so-called Mission Ocean Ecosystem (MOE). Chapter 3 gives an overview of the related domain belonging to the MOE as well as their top-level concepts.

2. Identify External Sources:

In addition to defining the ontology, particularly outlining its concepts and their interconnections, a crucial step involves identifying the external sources you intend to incorporate into your ontology, which may encompass research initiatives, funding prospects, databases, and related references.

The main source will be the MOE database (Task 4.1), which serves as the ground truth.

3. Select an Ontology Language:

With all the different domains which contribute to the MOE, The Comité international pour la documentation Conceptual Reference Model (in short CIDOC-CRM) has been chosen as a guidance for creating the MOE ontology. It has been proven to be a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage.

Chapter 4 gives a short overview of this conceptual reference model.

4. Define Core Concepts, Classes, Relationships:

Key classes of the MO ecosystem are defined based on core classes on CIDOC-CRM. Chapter 5 gives a short overview on how concepts of MOE are expressed as an extension to the existing representation. While preserving the open world assumption, this approach makes it easier to integrate additional data sources with their corresponding metadata schemes.

5. Create Instances:

Based on a graph database (neo4j²) a set of tools using the Python programming language has been developed to map existing data into instances of the MOE ontology, which serve as examples/guidelines of how to integrate data into the semantic network.

- Create projects from MOE database
- Create projects, results from CORDIS data
- Create controlled vocabulary (NACE, EuroSciVoc, EuroVoc, TRL)
- Create relations between projects, results, and controlled vocabulary.

6. Document and Annotate:

The MOE will follow the documentation style and guidelines from CIDOC-CRM. Concepts (see Appendix A - Entity Reference).

Chapter 6 contains the programming and usage guidance for the ontology and the semantic network. These guidelines mainly address developer and maintainer of the MOE database and the mission dashboard.

The next chapter Mission Ocean Ecosystem gives an overview of the current state for step 1 (define the Domain and Purpose/Consider reuse) and step 2 (Identify External Sources) in the ontology development workflow. It defines the domain and gives a reference for considered ontologies, vocabulary/thesauri and data sources.

² <https://neo4j.com/>
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Mission ontology

3 Mission Ocean Ecosystem

The purpose of the ontology is to enable semantic interoperability between all entities within the Mission Ocean Ecosystem (MOE). Semantic interoperability refers to the ability of different computer systems, applications, or data sources to exchange and understand information in a way that ensures sharing a common understanding of the meaning of that information. In simpler terms, it's about making sure that when different systems communicate, they understand each other's data and can use it correctly.

Figure 2 shows the current version of the MOE ecosystem map. It contains all the major domains and their top-level concepts, already existing ontologies/data schemes as well as related controlled vocabulary/thesauri.

Figure 2 Mission Ocean Ecosystem Ontology Map (MOEOM).

Centered around the Mission Ocean with its objectives and actions, there are five key areas contributing to the Mission Ocean ecosystem:

- RESEARCH
 - Projects and their direct results (publication, patents, etc.)
 - Extracted Knowledge Output according to Task 4.3.
- BUSINESS
 - Financial ecosystem including funding, business model, etc.
- ACTORS
 - Stakeholders and Citizens including the various methodologies for engagement
- LEGAL
 - Legal domain (EU regulations, directives, local laws, etc.)
- MARITIME
 - Marine domain (Digital twin of the ocean, WoRMS, etc.)

In this first version for the MOE ontology the focus was on the research and the actor domain aligned with the data stored MOE database.

For each of the five key areas outlined above, relevant ontologies, vocabularies/thesauri, and data sources are listed. These resources contribute either as support for design decisions or for enriching the data within the MOE database.

3.1 Actors Domain

3.1.1 Ontologies

FOAF

FOAF stands for "Friend of a Friend." It is an ontology and a set of conventions for creating machine-readable representations of people, their activities, and their relationships.

CIDOC-CRM institution information

Since the MOE ontology is based on CIDOC-CRM the default mechanism for defining actors (in particular E39-Actor and E74-Group) will be used for stakeholders and citizens. Figure 3 shows the default pattern of how to model institution information.

3.1.2 Vocabularies/Thesauri

Not applicable in the first version.

3.1.3 Source

Not applicable in the first version.

3.2 Financial Domain

3.2.1 Ontologies

Not applicable in the first version.

3.2.2 Vocabularies/Thesauri

Nomenclature of Economic Activities (NACE)

NACE is the European standard classification of productive economic activities. It presents the universe of economic activities partitioned in such a way that a NACE code can be associated with a statistical unit carrying them out [CE08].

Figure 3 CIDOC-CRM modeling of institution information [CID].

3.2.3 Source

Not applicable in the first version.

3.3 Research Domain

3.3.1 Ontologies

European Research Information Ontology (EURIO)

EURIO has been developed by CORDIS on the basis of data about research projects funded by the EU's framework programmes for research and innovation following Semantic Web standards. EURIO is aligned with EU ontologies such as DINGO and FRAPO and de facto standard ontologies such as schema.org and the Organization Ontology from W3C. Moreover, it models projects and actors such as people and organizations, while also including administrative information like funding schemes and grants.

Data Integration and Extension for Grant Ontology (DINGO)

DINGO, the Data Integration and Extension for Grant Ontology, is an ontology expressly designed to provide an extensible interoperable framework for formally conceptualizing and expressing the relevant parts of the research/cultural landscape in relation to funding, such that they can easily be shared between different actors and platforms.

3.3.2 Vocabularies/Thesauri

EuroSciVoc

EuroSciVoc is a multilingual taxonomy that represents all the main fields of science that were discovered from CORDIS content and organised through a semiautomatic process based on NLP techniques. It contains more than 1000 categories in 6 languages (English, French, German, Italian, Polish and Spanish) and each category is enriched with relevant keywords extracted from the textual description of CORDIS projects. It is specifically developed as a reference vocabulary for the Open Science community and is aligned with Linked Open Data standards.

3.3.3 Sources

EU funding programmes

EU funding programmes as well as funded projects can be retrieved using the "Community Research and Development Information Service" (CORDIS). It is the European Union's (EU) primary online portal for information related to EU-funded research and innovation programs. CORDIS is managed by the European Commission and provides access to a wide range of information about EU-funded projects, research initiatives, and innovation activities. For the MOE ontology it is one of the main data sources.

National funding programs of the EU member states

In addition to EU-level research funding, it's important to note that there are also national research funding opportunities available within the European Union member states, like the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) as the central selfgoverning organization for academic research in Germany.

3.4 Legal Domain

3.4.1 *Ontologies*

European Legislation Identifier (ELI)

The European Legislation Identifier (ELI) is a framework to make legislation metadata available online in a standardised format, so that it can be accessed, exchanged and reused across borders[otE].

3.4.2 *Vocabularies/Thesauri*

EuroVoc

EuroVoc is a multilingual, multidisciplinary thesaurus developed and maintained by the Publications Office of the European Union. It is a standardized vocabulary that serves as a tool for indexing, categorizing, and retrieving documents and information related to the European Union (EU) and its institutions. EuroVoc is used primarily for the classification and retrieval of documents within the EU's various language versions, making it easier to access and understand EU-related content in multiple languages. EuroVoc is used in ELI as a standardized and multilingual thesaurus that helps classify, index, and categorize legal documents within the EU.

3.4.3 *Source*

Not applicable in the first version.

3.5 Maritime Domain

3.5.1 *Ontologies*

Not applicable in the first version.

3.5.2 *Vocabularies/Thesauri*

World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS)

The "World Register of Marine Species" (WoRMS) is an online database that aims to provide a comprehensive and authoritative list of all known marine species in the world. It is a global initiative led by the Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ) in Belgium, and it involves collaboration with a vast network of marine scientists and taxonomists from around the world. The primary goal of WoRMS is to create a standardized and up-to-date taxonomic and nomenclatural reference for marine species (see Figure 4).

WoRMS taxon details

★ ***Sphyrna zygaena* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

AphiaID	105819 (urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:tax-name:105819)
Classification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biota > ★ Animalia (Kingdom) > ★ Chordata (Phylum) > ★ Vertebrata (Subphylum) > ☆ Gnathostomata (Infraphylum) > ★ Chondrichthyes (Parvphylum) > ★ Elasmobranchii (Class) > ★ Neoselachii (Subclass) > ★ Selachii (Infraclass) > ☆ Galeomorphi (Superorder) > ★ Carcharhiniformes (Order) > ★ Sphyrnidae (Family) > ★ <i>Sphyrna</i> (Genus) > ★ <i>Sphyrna zygaena</i> (Species)
Status	accepted
Rank	Species
Typetaxon of	★ <i>Sphyrna Rafinesque, 1810</i>
Parent	★ <i>Sphyrna Rafinesque, 1810</i>
Orig. name	★ <i>Squalus zygaena</i> Linnaeus, 1758

★ To FishBase images ...

Figure 4 WoRMS webpage for hammerhead shark.

3.5.3 Sources

Not applicable in the first version.

3.6 Cross Cutting Principles

This section list cross cutting principles, which are not clearly belonging to one of the five key areas above, e.g. the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (Getty TGN or short TGN) can be for defining the location of stakeholders as well as location to which research projects contribute.

3.6.1 Vocabularies/Thesauri

Technical Readiness level

Technical Readiness Level (TRL) is a concept used in various industries, particularly in engineering, aerospace, and technology, to assess the maturity and readiness of a technology or innovation for practical application. It provides a standardized way to measure the progress of a technology from the early research stages to its readiness for commercialization and deployment. TRL levels are defined with specific criteria, making it a valuable tool for decision-making, funding allocation, and project management.

The nine TRL levels as defined in the "HORIZON 2020 – WORK PROGRAMME 2014-2015 General Annexes" are:

- TRL 1 – basic principles observed
- TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4 – technology validated in lab
- TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
- TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
- TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN)

The Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN) is a structured vocabulary and database that provides information about places, including geographical names, historical names, and other related data. It is maintained and published by the Getty Research Institute, a part of the J. Paul Getty Trust, which is known for its involvement in art research and cultural heritage.

The TGN helps standardize and control the use of geographic names to ensure consistency in cataloging and documentation. Figure 5 shows the webpage which resolves TGN id 1000003 to Europe.

Click the icon to view the hierarchy.

[Semantic View \(JSON, JSONLD, RDF, N3/Turtle, N-Triples\)](#)

ID: 1000003 Record Type: **physical**

Page Link: <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/tgn/1000003>

 Europe (continent)

Coordinates:
 Lat: 56 12 00 N degrees minutes Lat: 56.2000 decimal degrees
 Long: 015 01 00 E degrees minutes Long: 15.0160 decimal degrees

Note: Europe was an early home to Homo erectus, Neanderthal and modern Homo sapiens. Agricultural settlements arose in the 7th millennium BCE. Advanced civilizations developed here in the Mediterranean area with Asian and African influences. Modern European nations began to form after the fall of the Western Roman Empire in the fifth century CE. The late 20th and early 21st centuries have witnessed the formation and expansion of the European Union, a group of European nations allied for trade and some administrative purposes, such as a common currency.

Names:

- Europe (**preferred**, C.O. English-P.U.N)
(French)
- Europa (C.O. Swedish)
(Basque)
(Catalan)
(Spanish)
(Norwegian)
(Romanian)
(Portuguese)
(Polish)

Figure 5 TGN Example for the place Europe.

4 CIDOC CRM

The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CRM)³ is a theoretical and practical tool for information integration in the field of cultural heritage. It can help researchers, administrators and the public explore complex questions with regards to our past across diverse and dispersed datasets. The CIDOC CRM achieves this by providing definitions and a formal structure for describing the implicit and explicit concepts and relationships used in cultural heritage documentation and of general interest for the querying and exploration of such data. Such models are also known as formal ontologies. These formal descriptions allow the integration of data from multiple sources in a software and schema agnostic fashion [BBD+21]. Schema-agnostic in this context means that data from different sources needs to be aligned, because for example the data format for research projects provided by CORDIS is different from the format provided by UN Decade.

The CIDOC CRM has been developed in a manner that is intended to promote a shared understanding of cultural heritage information by providing a common and extensible semantic framework for evidence-based cultural heritage information integration. It is intended to be a common language for domain experts and implementers to formulate requirements for information systems and to serve as a guide for good practice of conceptual modelling. In this way, it can provide the "semantic glue" needed to mediate between different sources of cultural heritage information, such as that published by museums, libraries and archives.

The CIDOC CRM is the outcome of over 20 years of development and maintenance work, originally by the CIDOC Documentation Standards Working Group and, presently, by the CIDOC CRM SIG, both of which are working groups of CIDOC. Since December, 2006, it has been recognized as an official ISO standard. This status was renewed in 2014 and can be found at ISO 21127:2014. The CIDOC CRM is a living standard that is designed in such a way as to provide both high level information retrieval and the formulation and documentation of very specific data points and questions. The CIDOC CRM thus consists of the CRMbase standard which provides the basic classes and relations devised for the cultural heritage world.

This CRMbase (base ontology) is complemented by a series of modular extensions to the basic model. Such extensions are designed to support different types of specialized research questions and documentation such as bibliographic documentation or geoinformatics. The CIDOC CRM extensions are developed in partnership with the research communities in question. These extensions are formulated in a manner that is harmonized with the base ontology such that data expressed in any extension is compatible with the base system of concepts and relations. This harmonized development process leads to a high level of information integrity and integration not available in other information systems.

³ CIDOC CRM V7.1.1 <https://doi.org/10.26225/FDZH-X261>

The base concepts and their typical connection/interaction between them are highlighted in Figure 6:

1. E55 Type:
 - *Definition:* E55 Type is a class representing a category or class of entities. It is used to classify entities into specific types or categories.
 - *Example:* If you have an entity representing a painting, its E55 Type might be "Oil Painting" or "Watercolor."
2. E41 Appellation:
 - *Definition:* E41 Appellation represents the assignment of a name or label to an entity. It is used to capture different names or titles associated with an entity.
 - *Example:* If you have an entity representing a person, the E41 Appellation might include different names or titles that person is known by.
3. E39 Actors:
 - *Definition:* E39 Actors represent individuals or corporate bodies that play a role in events or activities. It includes both human and non-human agents.
 - *Example:* A person (human) attending an exhibition or a software agent (non-human) updating a database.
4. E2 Temporal Entities:
 - *Definition:* E2 Temporal Entities represent periods or instances in time. It is used to model temporal aspects of entities, events, and activities.
 - *Example:* A specific date (instance) or a time span (period) associated with the creation of a cultural artifact.
5. E28 Conceptual Objects:
 - *Definition:* E28 Conceptual Objects represent abstract or conceptual entities that are not physical. They are used to model ideas, concepts, or intellectual creations.
 - *Example:* The concept of "justice" or an abstract idea represented in a philosophical text.
6. E18 Physical Thing:
 - *Definition:* E18 Physical Thing represents tangible, physical entities. It is a superclass for all entities that have a material existence.
 - *Example:* A sculpture, a book, or any object that has a physical form.
7. E53 Places:
 - *Definition:* E53 Places represent locations or spaces. It is used to model places or areas associated with events, objects, or actors.
 - *Example:* The Louvre Museum (as a place) where a painting (as an object) is exhibited, or the birthplace of an individual.

These concepts are foundational elements in the CIDOC CRM and are used to model various aspects of cultural heritage information, providing a standardized way to describe entities, events, and their relationships. Figure 1 shows these foundational elements and their available refinements.

CIDOC-CRM has already been used in the maritime domain as part of the SeaLiT⁴ project as an extension for the modelling of Maritime History Information. Figure 8 displays the newly introduced SeaLiT concepts with the blue boxes.

Figure 6 Base classes of CIDOC CRM.

⁴ Seafaring Lives in Transition, Mediterranean Maritime Labour and Shipping
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Figure 7 CIDOC-CRM class hierarchy.

Figure 8 SeaLiT definition of ship and voyage.

Part 2: Developer Guidance

5 MOE Ontology

5.1 Notation

To distinct the new PREP4BLUE concepts from the original concepts of CIDOC-CRM, entities are numbered starting the prefix "B" for classes and "BP" for properties and a unique number, e.g., **B1-Mission**. Figure 9 shows the used notation for the concept diagrams.

The reference of the MOE entities (see chapter 6) follows the design of the entity description of the CIDOC-CRM.

Figure 9 Notation for the concept's diagrams.

5.2 Concepts

This section introduces the main concepts/classes of the PREP4BLUE extension of CIDOC-CRM as well as examples from the semantic network. The complete list of classes and properties is available in chapter 6.

5.2.1 Mission and Objectives

The central element of the MOE ontology are the concepts of a mission and their objectives (see Figure 10). The mission objectives **B3-Mission Objective** are defined as components of **B1-Mission** using **P148-has-component**. A Mission objective can have other Mission Objectives as their subcomponent or refer to another objective (e.g. from a different mission (see Figure 18 for an example)).

Figure 10 Mission and Mission Objectives of MOE.

5.2.2 Project

The **B2-Project** represents a (funded) research project, which exposes the characteristic of an **E7-Activity** as an activity over time as well as a **E89-PropositionalObject** that are "about" something in the sense of an research topic or idea (see Figure 11). Using **P67-refers-to** it can refer to a MOE location (e.g. the North sea).

Connecting Actors

B2-Mission as a subclass of **E7-Activity** connects to an actor who actively participates in the project using the **P14-carried-out-by** attribute. Actor can either be an instance of an individual person (**E21-Person**) or an organisation (**E74-Group**) (e.g. a University, Interest Group, etc.).

Figure 11 A project within the MOE.

Timeline

The chronological order of a project is archived by connecting the **E52-Time-Span** using the **P2-has-time-span** attribute of **E7-Activity**. A follow-up mission can be expressed using **P134-continued**. Mission (sub missions) segments can be modelled using the **P10-falls-within** attribute. Figure 12 expresses that the PREP4BLUE mission lasts from 2022 to 2025 and was continued by the PREPBLUE NG project. In addition mission PREP4BLUE consists of the two (sub)missions PREP4BLUE WP1 and PREP4BLUE WP2.

Publications

Project outputs (e.g., publications or other deliverables) are added using the standard information model for integrating DC metadata. This is connected to the project using a **E35-Creation**, which also connects the authors **E39-Actor** as outlined in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Timespan and chronological order of projects (Prep4Blue project as an example).

Figure 13 Example of a mission with (actively) involved persons and organisations.

5.2.3 Knowledge Output

As defined in WP4 Knowledge Output (KO) is defined as follows:

This class comprises a unit of knowledge or learning generated by or through research activity. They are not limited to de-novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know how/ knowledge.

A Knowledge Output is not: A theory, hypothesis or idea. Potential results or outputs. A Scientific publication, deliverables or report but these may contain one or multiples KOs.

Figure 14 Knowledge Output

Figure 14 shows the definition of **B4-Knowledge Output** which can refer to a mission objective. Attached KPI to the KO (like TRL, SDG, etc.) are attached as instances of **E55-Type**.

5.2.4 Engagement methods

This class comprises methods of citizen/stakeholder engagement. As a method it exposes characteristic of **E29-Design-or-Procedure**. The engagement method is connected to a project by **P33-used-specific-technique** (see Figure 15).

Figure 15 Attached engagement methods to a project.

6 Usage guidance

The usage guidance is divided into two parts. The first section 6.1 gives a short introduction of how to browse/navigate the semantic network using the standard tools available for the Neo4j graph database. The second section 6.2 gives examples of how to use the Python tools to build the semantic network.

6.1 Semantic Network

The current version of semantic network based on the first version of the ontology is stored on a Neo4j instance available at <http://prep4blue.ddd.fraunhofer.at:7474/browser/>. The semantic network can be accessed using either the Neo4j Browser or Neo4j Bloom. A more sophisticated user interface to the semantic network will be available within the MOE dashboard (Task 4.5 - Pilot tracking of Mission Implementation and tools for assessing progress towards targets).

6.1.1 Neo4j Browser

Neo4j Browser is a versatile and user-friendly application that serves as a centralized hub for developers and data professionals to manage and work with Neo4j. This platform provides a convenient and intuitive graphical interface, enabling users to create, configure, and maintain Neo4j databases effortlessly. Neo4j Desktop simplifies the process of launching and managing Neo4j instances, offering tools for database creation, schema design, data import, and query execution. It also supports the installation and management of plugins and extensions, making it a valuable tool for exploring the capabilities of Neo4j and developing graph-based applications. Overall, Neo4j Desktop streamlines the development and administration of Neo4j databases, making it an indispensable resource for those involved in graph data modeling and analysis.

6.1.2 Neo4j Bloom

Neo4j Bloom is primarily a data visualization and exploration tool, designed to provide an intuitive and interactive way to visualize and analyze graph data stored in Neo4j databases. It is particularly useful for non-technical users and business analysts who want to explore data graphically and discover insights without writing complex queries.

Currently Neo4j Bloom is only available within the free Neo4j Desktop local database. The Neo4j Bloom User Interface Guide [NEOA] provides a good introduction as well as tutorial videos of how to use Neo4j Bloom.

6.1.3 Neo4j Cypher Query

The Neo4j Ciper Query, also known as Cypher, is a powerful graph query language specifically designed for interacting with Neo4j's graph database. It allows users to express complex patterns and relationships within the graph data, making it a key tool for querying and manipulating data stored in Neo4j databases, facilitating efficient graph-based data retrieval and manipulation.

The basic syntax of a Neo4j Cypher query consists of the following components:

- **MATCH:** This is the first clause that specifies the pattern you want to match within the graph data. You define nodes, relationships, and their patterns to identify the data you're interested in.
- **WHERE:** Optionally, you can include a WHERE clause to filter the results based on specific conditions, such as property values or other criteria.
- **RETURN:** This clause is used to specify what data or variables you want to retrieve from the matched pattern. You can return nodes, relationships, properties, or computed values.
- **Optional clauses:** You can add additional clauses like CREATE, MERGE, SET, and DELETE to modify or create data in the graph. These clauses are often used for data manipulation.

Here's a simple example of a Cypher query:

```
MATCH (person:Person)-[:KNOWS]->(friend:Person)
WHERE person.name = 'Alice'
RETURN person, friend
```

In this query, we are matching a pattern where a node labeled "Person" named 'Alice' is connected to another node labeled "Person" through a "KNOWS" relationship. The WHERE clause filters the results to only include data where the person's name is 'Alice,' and the RETURN clause specifies that we want to retrieve the 'person' and 'friend' nodes that match the pattern. The Neo4j Cypher Refcards [neob] gives an overview of all available cypher commands.

Based on the first version of the MOE ontology, the following paragraphs show examples of how to query the semantic network:

NACE classification

The following cypher query displays the first three levels of the NACE hierarchy (see Figure 16):

```
//NACE Classification
MATCH p=(n:E55Type{value:"NACE"})-[:P127IHasNarrowerTerm*0..3]->(
  E55Type)
RETURN p
```

EuroSciVoc classification

The following cypher query displays the first three levels of the EuroSciVoc hierarchy:

```
//EuroSciVoc Classification
MATCH p=(n:E55Type{value:"EuroSciVoc"})-[:P127IHasNarrowerTerm
  *0..3]->(E55Type)
RETURN p
```


Figure 16 Graph representation of NACE classification.

All missions with their objectives

The following cypher query list all missions with their corresponding objectives (see Figure 18):

```
//Mission Objectives
MATCH p=(m:B1Mission) -->(:B3MissionObjective)
RETURN p
```

All projects with reference to the Baltic Sea

The following cypher query lists all Missions, which refer to the Baltic Sea:

```
//Mission Objectives
MATCH p=(E53Place {uid:'TGN:7013200'}) <-[:P67RefersTo]-(:B2Project)
return p
```

6.2 Programming Guide

For creating the semantic network a tool library using the Python programming language is under development. The backbone of these python tools for prep4blue is cidoc-crm-neo4j1, which is a meta-implementation of the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model in Neo4j, using neomodel⁵. This package implements the CRM by dynamically creating model classes from the CRM RDF specification. This limits code maintenance, and makes it easy to switch among versions of the model[Pei]. For the semantic network of PREP4BLUE the original CRM RDF specification is exchanged by the version with the PREP4BLUE extension.

```
from neomodel import config
from neomodel import (config, db, StructuredNode, StringProperty,
                      IntegerProperty,
                      UniqueIdProperty, RelationshipTo)
from neomodel.properties import display_for
from . import models      # The correct way!

schema_location = './data/p4b-cidoc-crm-0.1.rdfs.xml'
models.build_models(schema_location, {"value":StringProperty,"uid":
                                     UniqueIdProperty,"url":StringProperty},)
```

It includes a subclass of neomodel.core.StructuredNode that implements a method called downcast, which re-instantiates a node instances using the most derivative class, or a target class that is a child of the node's current class. Combined with the fact that neomodel applies all tags in a class hierarchy to node instances and uses those labels to enforce relationship definitions, the result is a full implementation of heritable relationships (CRM properties).

prep4blue.py

The *prep4blue.py* script provides a convenience wrapper around the CIDOC crm-neo4j solution. The following snippets shows the basic initialization of the PREP4BLUE CRM model for Neo4j:

```
# Neo4J connection info
NEO_BOLT = 'bolt://neo4j:Prep4Blue@localhost:7687'
NEO_BOLT_SECURITY = False

models = p4b.Prep4Blue_CRM(NEO_BOLT, NEO_BOLT_SECURITY)
```

⁵ <https://neo4j.com/labs/neomodel/>
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get_or_create Convenience function to avoid boilerplate code for creating objects only if they do not exist. The following code snippet checks if an object with a given id and if not creates it.

```
m = models.B1Mission.nodes.first_or_none(uid="TGN:7013200")
if m is None:
    m = models.E53Place(value="Baltic Sea", uid="TGN:7013200", url="
http://vocab.getty.edu/page/tgn/7013200")
    m.save()
```

With the convenience function `get_or_create` this can be reduced to one line

```
m = p4b.get_or_create(models.E53Place, value="Baltic Sea", uid="TGN
:7013200", url="http://vocab.getty.edu/page/tgn/7013200")
```

clear_neo4j_database Removes all objects and relations from the Neo4j database.

build_index Defines the required indices for better performance. The cypher query `show indexes` shows all available indexes within the Neo4j database.

init_knowledgegraph.py

The *init_knowledgegraph.py* script to prepare the Neo4j with the basic data by performing the following tasks:

- Clearing the database (Warning: all existing data will be deleted!)
- Define the required indices for better performance
- Build the following classification schemes as CIDOC CRM types:
 - NACE
 - EuroSciVoc
 - TRL

build_missions.py

The *build_missions.py* script builds the Mission structure with their objectives for the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters 2030' and the UN Mission 'Ocean Decade'. The following snippet shows how to create the **B1-Mission** with the three objective **B3-Mission-Objective** and their relationship as **P148-has-component** (see Figure 17):

```

m = p4b.get_or_create(models.B1Mission,value="EU Mission '
Restore our Ocean and Waters 2030'", uid="MissionBlue", url="
https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-
opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-
missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters_en")
o1 = p4b.get_or_create(models.B3MissionObjective,value="MO 1 (
Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and
biodiversity)", uid="MissionBlue_01")
o2 = p4b.get_or_create(models.B3MissionObjective,value="MO 2 (
Prevent and eliminate pollution of our ocean, seas and waters)",
uid="MissionBlue_02")
o3 = p4b.get_or_create(models.B3MissionObjective,value="MO 3 (
Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular)",
uid="MissionBlue_03")

m.P148_has_component.connect(o1)
m.P148_has_component.connect(o2)
m.P148_has_component.connect(o3)

```


Figure 17 The EU Mission Ocean and Waters with its three objectives.

As an example, this script also connects the objectives of the UN Mission 'Ocean Decade' to the corresponding objectives of the EU Mission using **P67-refers-to**. Figure 18 shows the EU Mission and the UN Mission 'Ocean Decade'.

Figure 18 EU Mission and the UN Mission 'Ocean Decade'.

build_places.py

The *build_places.py* script the main places used within the MOE. This serves just as an example of how to integrate geographical data into the semantic network. It is recommended to insert the references to locations using the Getty TGN id just-in-time.

build_H2020_allprojects.py

The *build_H2020_allprojects.py* Imports all projects from the Horizon 2020 provided by CORDIS as **B2-Project** into the semantic network and connects them to the given EuroSciVoc terms. The following code snippet shows the creation of a **B2-Project**. In this first version timing reasoning is not included in the inserting process.

```
# build the B2 instance and link it to the given instance of
E53Place
def build_project(id, short_title, title, startDate, endDate,
abstract, doi, crm_location):
    p = models.B2Project.nodes.first_or_none(uid=id)
    if p is None:
        p = models.B2Project(value =f"[{short_title}] - {title}",
uid = id, url = f"https://doi.org/{doi}")
        p.save()
    if crm_location is not None:
        p.P67_refers_to.connect(crm_location)
```

build_H2020_publications.py

The *build_H2020_publications.py* imports all publications from the Horizon 2020 projects into the semantic network. Since the CORDIS data provides only the names of authors, these names are taken as the id. Currently co-references are not resolved, so every author is considered to be unique. This will be done in the future using other data sources like citation databases. The following code snippet shows the creation of a for the publication as well as their connection to the authors as [E39-Actor](#):

```
def build_publication(id,doi,title,project_id,authors):
    #lookup project
    project = models.B2Project.nodes.first_or_none(uid=project_id)
    if project is None: # don't include publication, when the project
is not there
        printEx(Fore.Red,f"warning: no project with id {project_id}
found!")
        return

    # create/get the authors
    author_nodes = []
    for a in str(authors).split(";"):
        author_nodes.append(p4b.get_or_create(models.E39Actor,value=
a,uid=a,url=""))

    pub = p4b.get_or_create(models.E31Document, value=f"{title}",
uid=doi, url=f"http://doi.org/{doi}")
    pub_creation = p4b.create(models.E65Creation, value="*",uid=f"
E65:{doi}")
    pub_creation.P94_has_created.connect(pub)
    for a in author_nodes:
        pub_creation.P14_carried_out_by.connect(a)

    pub_creation.P10_falls_within.connect(project)
```

7 Conclusion

With the first version of the MOE ontology, a formal representation as a structured framework that defines the relationships and concepts relevant to the Mission Ocean ecosystem domain, has been created.

Software tools have been created to facilitate the process of mapping data, which involves connecting and relating data points from the MOE database and other sources. These tools automate or streamline the process, ensuring efficiency and accuracy.

Using the MOE ontology and data mapping tools, a semantic network has been constructed. A semantic network represents the relationships between different concepts in a way that is understandable for machines.

The semantic network serves as the foundation for Task 4.5 - Pilot tracking of Mission Implementation and tools for assessing progress towards targets, which involves integrating this network into a final dashboard as a visual interface that provides a user-friendly way to interact with, and interpret the data represented in the semantic network.

Further development involves two main aspects:

- *Adding More Data Sources from the five key areas:*

Further development involves expanding the scope by incorporating additional data from five key areas.

- *Methods for automatic alignment of different concepts:*

To enhance the usability of the system, there's a focus on developing methods for automatically aligning different concepts. This could involve ensuring consistency in how concepts from various sources are represented and related within the semantic network.

8 Bibliography

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Appendix A - Entity Reference

The following reference follows the documentation style and guidelines of CIDOC-CRM and is extension to the CIDOC CRM 7.1.1⁶

⁶ <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/Version/version-7.1.1>
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Mission ontology

A Entity Reference

This chapter contains the definition of PREP4BLUE extension entites to the original CIDOC-CRM model.

A.1 B1 Mission

SubClass Of: [E7-Activity](#), [E89-Propositional-Object](#)

SuperClass Of: No superclasses found

Scope Note: This class comprises missions following the definition from the European Commission¹:

EU Missions are a new way to bring concrete solutions to some of our greatest challenges. They have ambitious goals and will deliver concrete results by 2030. They put research and innovation into a new role, combined with new forms of governance and collaboration, as well as by engaging citizens.

EU Missions are a novelty of the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme for the years 2021-2027.

Examples:

- Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030
- Mission Adaptation to Climate Change

In first Order Logic: $B2(x) \Rightarrow E7(x), B2(x) \Rightarrow E89(x)$

Outgoing Direct Properties:

B1-Mission P148-has-component : [B3-Mission-Objective](#)

¹https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe_en#what-are-eu-missions

A.2 B2 Project

SubClass Of: E7-Activity, E89-Propositional-Object

SuperClass Of: No superclasses found

Scope Note: This class comprises research projects which expose the characteristic of an E7-Activity as an activity over time as well as a E89-Propositional-Object that are "about" something in the sense of an research topic or idea.

Examples:

- PREP4BLUE project
- 3D-COFORM project

In first Order Logic: $B2(x) \Rightarrow E7(x), B2(x) \Rightarrow E89(x)$

Outgoing Direct Properties:

B1-Mission P148-has-component : B3-Mission-Objective

A.3 B3 Mission Objective

SubClass Of: E89-Propositional-Object

SuperClass Of: No superclasses found

Scope Note: This class comprises objectives, which are defined as key efforts to achieve within a mission.

Examples:

- Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity (Mission Restore our Oceans and Waters)
- Reduce land degradation relating to desertification (Mission A Soil Deal for Europe)

In first Order Logic: $B3(x) \Rightarrow E89(x)$

Outgoing Direct Properties:

B3-Mission-Objective P148-has-component : **B3-Mission-Objective**

Incoming Direct Properties:

B1-Mission P148-has-component : **B3-Mission-Objective**

A.4 B4 Knowledge Output

SubClass Of: **E89-Propositional-Object**

SuperClass Of: No superclasses found

Scope Note: This class comprises a unit of knowledge or learning generated by or through research activity. They are not limited to de novo or pioneering discoveries but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know how/ knowledge.

Examples:

In first Order Logic: $B4(x) \Rightarrow E89(x)$

A.5 B5 Engagement Method

SubClass Of: **E55-Type**

SuperClass Of: No superclasses found

Scope Note: This class comprises methods of citizen/stakeholder engagement. As a method it exposes characteristic of **E29-Design-or-Procedure**.

Examples:

- Participatory Planning
- Business match-making events

In first Order Logic: $B6(x) \Rightarrow E55(x)$